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THE ANALYSIS ROLE OF METAPHORS IN THE WORKS OF FICTION OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Annotation: This article is devoted to the study of the role of metaphor in the English language. The purpose of the work is to determine the purpose of metaphors, as well as to analyze the functional role of metaphors in the works of fiction of the English language. The relevance of this work is due to the ambiguity of the representation of metaphor as a linguistic unit. When used in speech, it carries a certain linguistic load. It is used in works of art to give the utterance an emotionally expressiveness shade.

Keywords: metaphor, phrase, functional role, hidden meaning

АНАЛИТИЧЕСКАЯ РОЛЬ МЕТАФОРОВ В ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННЫХ ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЯХ АНГЛОЯЗЫКА

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Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена изучению роли метафоры в английском языке. Цель работы определить назначение метафор, а также проанализировать функциональную роль метафор в произведениях художественной литературы на английском языке. Актуальность данной работы обусловлена неоднозначностью представления метафоры как языковой единицы. При употреблении в речи оно несет определенную языковую нагрузку. Он используется в художественных произведениях для придания высказыванию эмоционально-экспрессивного оттенка.

Ключевые слова: метафора, фраза, функциональная роль, скрытый смысл

Each language is beautiful and rich in its own way. A person studying it should know and be able to use different linguistic aspects: grammatical, morphological, phonetic, stylistic and others.

Translation from Russian into English and vice versa is a very difficult work. Stylistic tropes, especially metaphors, are even more difficult to translate. The predominance of metaphors is characteristic of works of art. The most difficult thing for a translator is to rethink works of fiction, where he must convey the meaning, and at the same time without changing the meaning of the word itself.

Although metaphor is an important means of expression, some linguists argue that metaphors violate the author's intention and make translation difficult. The fact is that a metaphor is a word, phrase or expression that is used in a hidden, figurative meaning based on a feature or similarity with an object. Unfortunately, foreigners do not always understand this hidden meaning. They have to study the whole context in order to understand the implicit content of the metaphor.

A huge number of works by scientists are devoted to the problems of studying metaphors [1-10]. So, Johnson and J. Lakoff argued that "metaphor permeates our everyday life, and not only language, but also thought and action... our usual conceptual system, in terms of which we think and act, is metaphorical in nature" [1, p. 3]. John Rogers Searle pointed out that the metaphor theory is based on the idea that consciousness is an abstract mechanism that processes raw data, its internal structure correlates with perceived objects and phenomena and therefore depends on them [2]. According to J.Fauconnier, it is natural for a person to understand one area through the prism of another, i.e. to carry out the transfer from the source area to the target area and reflect this in the language [3, p. 24]. According to Bobrova T.O. metaphor is a fundamental phenomenon for human language and conceptualization, with the help of metaphor people form an idea of the world and their occupations [7]. Metaphors set analogies and associations between different systems of concepts and generate particular metaphors. There are different types of metaphors: universal metaphors that manifest themselves in different languages and cultures, and metaphors that are

culturally specific. Nartikova Z.A. and Zaitseva O.L. believe that the difference in the metaphorical means used is explained by cultural factors [8]. Pavlenko V.G. differentiates metaphorical models into universal and culturally specific ones [9-10].

Despite such a huge number of works devoted to this problem, the question of the purpose of the metaphor still remains unresolved. There are still differences in the linguistic understanding of this trope in the scientific society. However, the concepts and processes that influenced the formation of the metaphor were identified.

There are metaphors in English that should not be translated verbatim. So, for example:

1. My brother was boiling mad (My brother was boiling like a madman) – this does not mean that he has gone mad, he is just angry [11].
2. Her voice is music to his ears (Her voice is music to his ears) – i.e. he is always happy to hear her voice [10].
3. Life is a journey (Life is a journey) – the depth of the phrase is that there are ups and downs in life, it is as different as traveling [11].
4. The assignment was a breeze (the task was in one breath) – i.e. very easy. In Russian, we would say "just spit" [11].

Let's consider some types of metaphors: [12].

1. A simple metaphor, for example: "the eye of heaven" (heavenly eye). Such metaphors are used in poetic texts where the author expresses his feelings and experiences in this way. At the same time, it can turn into hyperbole if it is based on exaggeration.
2. A detailed metaphor. These metaphors are most often used when composing riddles. And they can affect several images at once, making up a single one: A woman is a foreign land (All women are from another planet).
3. Plot metaphor. The most interesting metaphor, due to its prevalence. It can often be found in novels as a compositional metaphor. A compositional metaphor is a phrase that only in this work serves as a metaphor: to pull strings.
4. A traditional metaphor. Common metaphors that serve as a description of qualities, appearance, etc. For example: a sunny smile (a shining smile).

There are also composite metaphors. This happens when a noun and an adjective are connected. In such cases, they acquire one meaning, unlike the

one that was separately. So, for example, the word "bloodbath", if translated literally, will turn out to be a bloodbath, but in fact the word translates as

"massacre". Or the word mind (mind, mind) and games (game) in total gives mindgames – a puzzle. And a few more examples: a nutcase is crazy, hard-bitten is persistent, soul-searching is introspection.

A metaphor is a linguistic unit that carries a linguistic load. Therefore, it is appropriate to highlight the main functions of the metaphor [12].

Nominative function. It is used when naming any objects or phenomena in an expressive form. For example, the English name Jerry means "ruler of the spear". Nominative functions are more clearly depicted at the interlanguage level. The image can when translating words.

Text-forming function. It helps the metaphor to take an expanded form: He likes to sleep in open...(he likes to sleep in open..)

Genre function. When metaphorical properties participate in the creation of a genre. For example, the riddle: I have no spur to prick the sides of my intent – I have no spurs to spur my intentions (horse).

Game function. This metaphor is often used if it is expressed by a saying, a proverb, etc. For example: grow big but do not be like noodles (grow big, but don't be noodles).

Conspiracy function. This is masking a metaphor as such. It is present in the text in a hidden sense: the fever of the soul, wasted in the desert (the heat of the soul, wasted in the desert).

In metaphor, words take on a new meaning. So, for example, the word "peach" (peach) acquires the meaning of sweet, juicy, ripe, if it is transformed into the metaphor "woman is a peach" (peach woman) [13].

If you replace the metaphor with an ordinary word in its direct meaning, the speech will not have such a vivid character. In order for speech to be rich and beautiful, you need to feel the line between a metaphor and a new word. However, scientists have not yet come to a consensus on the relationship between metaphor and extended meaning.

Vivid metaphors are found in the works of English writers [14].

For example, in A. Huxley's work "Point Counter Point", the metaphor: "the emotion was always flowing" (emotion always flows) implicitly expresses the emotional state of a character whose mood fluctuates from loving feelings to hostile ones: "One way or the other, the emotion was always flowing. There were hardly any intervals of comfortably slack water. The tide was always running».

Metaphors can be a reference to any work. For example, the metaphor of the same author: "funeral baked meats" in the statement "Monday's funeral baked meats did service for Tuesday's wedding" resembles lines from Hamlet and implicitly implies readiness for the funeral of his father.

In addition, authors often resort to using metaphors to express a satirical effect. Zoometaphors serve to create an atmosphere of comicality, namely, comparisons of a person with animals, while the author highlights the characteristics of animals, thereby emphasizing the positive or negative qualities of a person. For example, K. Boyle, in his work "On the Run" uses the metaphor: "soft pink tide of pigs", compares a person with an animal, which makes a person's appearance more saturated and bright and funny: "As the train stopped a soft pink tide of pigs rose out of the station-yard".

Often authors personify their characters, endow animals with human qualities. So, in the work of W. Shakespeare "Hamlet" in the statement of the hero Horatio: The cock, that is the trumpet to the morn, / Dot with his lofty and shrill sounding throat / Awake the god of day) the author uses the metaphor: "the cock is trumpet to the morn" as a personification, where he compares the rooster with the trumpeter of the dawn, who with his high and ringing throat wakes up from the day god's dream.

Also, a large number of metaphors are found in dramaturgical works.

In T. Williams' play "A Streetcar Named Desire", the metaphor is "The Grim Reaper had put up his tent on our doorstep..." (The Grim Reaper put his tent on our doorstep!) the author refers us to Longfellow's poem "The Reaper and the Flowers"(reaper and flowers). This metaphor implicitly expresses the meaning of life and death. The Flower of Death is an iconic Reaper ability that poses a danger to opponents.

The following metaphor in his play: "pearls before swine" (to throw beads in front of pigs!) It comes from the work Sermon on the Mount: "But I have been foolish—casting my pearls before swine" expresses the meaning of a vain conversation about something or proof of something to someone who is unable or unwilling to understand or appreciate.

In the same play by T. Williams, the metaphor: "treasures locked in my heart" implies the presence of intelligence, common sense as a treasure: «How strange that I should be called a destitute woman! When I have all these treasures locked in my heart».

T. Williams in the work "Suddenly Last Summer" discusses the meaning of life and uses a metaphor: "trails of debris" (dust), where a person is

compared to dust: "Most people's lives—what are they but trails of debris, each day more debris... with nothing to clean it all up but, finally, death".

Based on the analysis of the works of fiction by English writers, we come to the conclusion that metaphors are an integral part of any works. They adorn speech and give the text emotionality, expressiveness and expressiveness.

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